

EuroMix

European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures

Project number 633172

Collaborative project
H2020-SFS-2014-2

Deliverable D2.3 – Report

Report on the use of the *Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC)* for the prioritisation of substances and mixtures thereof

WP 2– QSAR and TTC approaches for setting test priorities

Due month of deliverable: Month 24 (May 2017)
Actual submission month: Month 30 (October 2017)

Deliverable leader: RIVM, NL

Document status: version 1, final

Creation date: 27/10/2017

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the H2020 Programme		
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	x
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	

Deliverable D2.3

Report on the use of *the Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC)* for the prioritisation of substances and mixtures thereof

October 2017

Deliverable D2.3

Report on the use of *the Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC)* for the prioritisation of substances and mixtures thereof

Authors: Emiel Rorije¹, Ivano Eberini², Ad Peijnenburg³

¹ RIVM, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, The Netherlands;

² University of Milan, Italy

³ RIKILT, Wageningen University and Research Centre, The Netherlands

Abstract

This deliverable explores the use of TTC and the TTC concepts (using distributions of NOAELs to derive “safe” thresholds) for the use of filling data gaps in the cumulative risk assessment of mixtures or combined exposures.

In the cumulative risk assessment the contribution of individual substances in the mixture or the combined exposure are added assuming dose additivity as a first tier worst case assumption. Adding the contributions of individual components is achieved through calculation of *relative potency factors*, which are ideally based on NOAELs from in vivo experiments. When NOAELs are lacking the TTC concept can provide a realistic worst case estimate of a NOAEL, which can subsequently be used to derive relative potency factors towards a single well studied reference compound.

In this deliverable the original TTC values from the Munro dataset have been reproduced, to allow the calculation of confidence intervals around the 5th percentiles of the NOAEL distributions, and/or sample the dataset directly in Monte Carlo simulation in order to allow probabilistic risk assessment approaches.

Derivation of CAG specific TTC-like thresholds is demonstrated for the case of hepatotoxicity/steatosis. This can be seen as a first step in refinement of the TTC-based relative potency factor estimation.

A second refinement in estimating more realistic potency factors based in absence of experimental data is the use of molecular docking calculations for comparison of potency of substances which are supposed to exert their toxic effect through the interaction with a specific receptor. Calculated binding energies are expected to give an indication of the (relative) potencies of those substances that trigger the same receptor.

Contents

Abstract	3
Introduction	5
Methods	7
Cramer classification	7
Distribution analyses	8
Results	9
The TTC derivation scheme and its place in the EuroMix workflow	9
TTC derivation	11
Cramer class I (low toxicity)	13
Cramer class II (moderately toxic).....	14
Cramer class III (high toxicity)	15
Calculation of TTC values for the Euromix Inventory.....	16
The use of CAG specific TTC-like values to estimate relative potency factors.....	16
The use of Molecular Docking Binding Energies to estimate relative potency factors	18
Conclusions	19
References.....	20
Annex 1. NOAEL Dataset used for determining TTC (Munro, 1996)	21

Introduction

The aim of task 2.3 was to establish procedures that would enable first tier (worst case) potency estimates based on the TTC concept).

In task 2.2, methodology has been explored to determine Cumulative Assessment Group (CAG) memberships, based on chemical structure alone. EuroMix Deliverable 2.2 describes the application of existing (Quantitative) Structure-Activity ((Q)SAR) and/or Molecular Docking models to indicate whether the risk of a single component in a mixture or cumulative exposure should be assessed together with for a particular effect, or can be ignored as it is predicted not to contribute to that specific toxicological effect. This concept of Cumulative Assessment Grouping is described in EFSA opinions ; the levels distinguished are CAG level 1: organ effects (e.g. liver toxicity, developmental toxicity); CAG level 2: phenomenological effect (e.g. Steatosis or Necrosis as a phenomenological effect in Liver toxicity); CAG level 3 and/or 4: mode of action/mechanism of action (e.g. cellular processes that can be determined by in vitro assays, such as accumulation of fatty acids in the liver cell (CAG level 3) or specific (nuclear) receptor interactions linked to a certain pathway of toxicity (CAG level 4). This procedure as proposed in EuroMix Deliverable 2.2 in effect predicts whether a certain effect will be observed after exposure to a specific substance, but it does however not give any information on the potency, or dose, at which this effect is thought to occur. To be able to accumulatively assess the risk of a mixture of chemicals, it is needed to also have an indication about the potency of the individual mixture components. The potency of a chemical is expressed as the NOAEL (from a long term toxicity study). By taking the ratio of the NOAELs with regard to one well studied reference compound, one can derive *relative* potency factors. These relative potency factors are used to add up the risk of different components thought to contribute to the same toxicological effect.

In the absence of *in vivo* long term toxicity data it is needed to derive a worst case estimate of a NOAEL for these compounds, which can be used derive a first tier (worst case) relative potency factor in the cumulative risk assessment of a mixture or combined exposure. For this purpose the concept of Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) is considered a good first tier, worst case, approach.

For the list of chemicals produced in task 2.1 (the EuroMix Inventory), TTCs were calculated as a first tier (worst case) estimate of the NOAEL, which can be used to determine Relative Potency Factors in absence of more specific (*in vivo*) data for specific mixture components. The TTC concept relies on the evaluation of a large set of *in vivo* long term toxicity studies and the *lowest* No Adverse Effect Level (NOAEL) that could be derived from these studies. The underlying assumption of the TTC concept is that the NOAELs coming from this evaluation will show a (log) normal distribution, allowing for determination of e.g. the 1st, 5th or 10th

percentile from this distribution as a starting point for the derivation of a *generally* applicable threshold where no effect is to be expected from any substance.

Munro (Munro 1996) evaluated a large dataset (613 organic substances) that are the basis of the TTC-values as they are applied today in risk assessment, especially in food and feed risk assessment (EFSA 2012, EFSA 2016a, EFSA 2016b).

Apart from the use of TTC for a first approach to estimating a worst case NOAEL where no other information is available, also the use of molecular docking analyses are a promising tool as they provide quantitative results (receptor binding energies), and potency factors may be derived based on these binding energies of a molecule to a receptor. A procedure to perform this translation of binding energy to (relative) potency is briefly indicated in this deliverable as well.

Methods

The Chemical inventories produced in Task 2.1 were used as the source of chemicals with which to apply *in silico* methods appropriate for determination of the appropriate Threshold of Toxicological Concern of individual chemical structures.

The chemicals were run through different software models for the determination of the correct Threshold of Toxicological concern. The software used is described in more detail below. Two dimensional structures were needed as input to the software; these were taken from the EuroMix inventory, with the derivation of the chemical structures described in detail in EuroMix deliverable 2.2

Cramer classification

The Cramer classification scheme (tree) is probably the best known approach for structuring chemicals in order to make a TTC estimation (Cramer, 1978). The tree relies primarily on chemical structures and estimates of total human intake to establish priorities for testing. The procedure uses recognized pathways for metabolic deactivation and activation, toxicity data and the presence of a substance as a component of traditional foods or as an endogenous metabolite. Substances are classified into one of three classes:

- Class I contains substances of simple chemical structure with known metabolic pathways and innocuous end products which suggest a low order of oral toxicity.
- Class II contains substances that are intermediate. They possess structures that are less innocuous than those in Class 1 but they do not contain structural features that are suggestive of toxicity like those in Class 3.
- Class III contains substances with chemical structures that permit no strong initial impression of safety and may even suggest a significant toxicity.

Different software exists that can perform the derivation of the Cramer classes automated for large datasets of chemical structures. For the EuroMix project the (freely available) implementation of the Cramer Classification in the ToxTree software is used, version 2.6.13 (ToxTree, 2017). The same classification is e.g. also available in the OECD QSAR Application Toolbox (OECD, 2017). The decision tree in the ToxTree software used is the “Cramer rules, with extensions” as described in (Lapenna, 2017).

Distribution analyses

To reproduce the derivation of the 5th percentiles from the Munro dataset we applied Microsoft for Excel, more specifically the normal and the log normal distribution functions NORM.INV and LOGNORM.INV. To derive the (left-tailed) Students T-test 5th percentile the T.INV function was used.

To fit the Munro NOEL data using log normal distributions the Graphpad Prism version 7.0.3 software was used.

The dataset from the original TTC publication by Munro is attached as an excel table to this Deliverable and given in Annex I. It should be noted that the original NOEL values from the Munro publication represent NOEL values with different exposure durations, and in order to derive a (chronic, life-time) TTC value, a subchronic-to-chronic extrapolation factor of 3 has been applied to all NOELs from sub-chronic duration studies. This is in line with the original data treatment from Munro, and reflects the normal assessment factor of 3 regularly applied in different Risk Assessment frameworks to sub-chronic studies. E.g. in the REACH derivation of DNELs also an assessment factor of 3 is used to extrapolate from sub-chronic exposure data (REACH, 2012).

Results

The TTC derivation scheme and its place in the EuroMix workflow

The TTC derivation scheme, (EFSA 2012, 2016a, 2016b) with the appropriate TTC values for the different classes is given below:

It should be noted that there are a large number of exceptions when the TTC concept is considered not-applicable, mainly due to concerns that toxicity CAN occur at lower doses (e.g. endocrine substances, nano-forms of specific materials), that substance classes were not-, or under-represented in the original Munro

database used to derive the TTC values (e.g. metallo-organic compounds, metals, inorganics), or that the substance might exert long term effects due to bioaccumulative behaviour, leading to substantially higher internal concentrations over longer time courses than can be expected based on the exposure duration in the toxicology testing performed to derive the TTC values. All these exceptions have to be taken into account when applying the TTC concept in the EuroMix workflow.

The classes “genotoxic carcinogens” and “organo-phosphates and –carbarnates” with their respective TTC values are not applicable to the EuroMix workflow, as both effects are not relevant for the case studies in EuroMix (Liver toxicity, Developmental toxicity and Endocrine disruption). Furthermore the EFSA opinions prescribe to group Cramer class II substances (moderate toxicity, TTC 540 ug/person/day) with the Cramer class III (high toxicity, TTC 90 ug/person/day) and use only the more conservative value of 90 ug/person/day for both Cramer classes. In the EuroMix workflow we do distinguish Cramer class II substances as a separate class, and we apply the original 5th percentile as derived by Munro (Munro, 1996) to this class.

Furthermore, the derived TTC values include an additional safety factor of 100, applied to the 5th percentile of the NOEL distribution. In the EuroMix workflow missing NOEL values from *in vivo* experiments have to be replaced with a *realistic worst case* estimate of the NOEL. Hence, we do not apply the derived TTC, but instead use the 5th percentile of the NOEL distributions directly (without the extra safety factor of 100 applied). In the EuroMix workflow this gives us the following logic to derive Relative Potency Factors:

TTC derivation

Using the original dataset from Munro (Munro, 1996) the derivation of the 5th percentiles from the distributions of the Cramer Classes I, II and III have been reproduced for this Deliverable. In the original derivation Munro actually used a crude log normal fit (using bins) of the NOAEL values of the substance to establish the 5th percentile. It is expected that using the lognormal distribution function in Excel should give a close approximation to the originally derived values from Munro.

In order to reproduce the original TTC value derivation, fits were applied to the data in order to derive a *fitted* 5th percentile, and in order to be able to derive uncertainty intervals around these 5th percentiles, which can subsequently be used in the Refine and Retain approach in EuroMix to create a *distribution* of TTC values which can be treated probabilistically in deriving the relative potency factors. In the implementation of the TTC in the EuroMix tool actually not the derived TTC values and the confidence intervals are used, but the original data (the 613 substance dataset of NOELs) is used directly to sample from in MonteCarlo simulation. This probabilistic treatment of the TTC as input for the relative potency factors will be discussed in other Deliverables, most notably from work package 6 in EuroMix. The derivation of the TTCs from this original dataset is therefore a quality check to see if the original values reported by Munro can be reproduced sufficiently precise. If this is the case we can use the original dataset (and the distribution over the three Cramer classes) for MonteCarlo simulation, having established that this should lead to the same Threshold Levels as derived originally by Munro, and still applied and recommended in recent EFSA opinions (EFSA, 2012, 2016a, 2016b).

In the Munro publication also a non-parametric derivation of the 5th percentile is mentioned, and for comparison this non-parametric derivation is also included in the reproduction. This non-parametric fit does not serve any other purpose as it does not give us confidence intervals for the probabilistic treatment of the TTC values.

When using the whole dataset (613 substances) to derive a generally applicable TTC value the following data were reproduced:

	In tranformed NOEL	NOEL TTC (mg/kg bw/day)	NOEL TTC Munro 1996 (mg/kg bw/day)
Whole dataset			
mean	2.87	17.65	n.d.
sd	2.63		
n	613		
5% lognorm	-1.46	0.23	0.22
5% students t distr.	-1.46	0.23	
log normal fit (Graphpad Prism)			
mean	2.947		
sd	2.65		
n	613		
5% lognorm	-1.41	0.24	0.22
5% students t distr.	-1.42	0.24	
Non parametric "fit"			
5%	-1.61	0.20	0.22

The publication by Munro mentions a TTC value of 0.22 mg/kg bw/day as the 5th percentile of the whole dataset (613 substances). The nonparametric fit to the data (taking the highest NOEL value of the 5% substances, i.e. the 31 most toxic substances) gives a value of 0.2 mg/kg bw/day. Using the excel lognormal distribution function, and the students t-distribution function yields a value of 0.23 mg/kg bw/day. Performing a log normal fit to the distribution (using the Graphpad Prism software) gives us a value of 0.24 mg/kg bw/day for the 5th percentile. All are sufficiently close to the value mentioned, given small rounding errors etc.

Cramer class I (low toxicity)

Values reproduced from the Munro dataset for the subclass of Cramer class I substances (137 substances) gives the following values for the TTC:

	In transformed NOEL	NOEL TTC (mg/kg bw/day)	NOEL TTC Munro 1996 (mg/kg bw/day)
Cramer Class I			
mean	4.79	119.84	116
sd	2.19		
n	137		
5% lognorm	1.19	3.29	3.0
5% students t distr.	1.17	3.21	
log normal fit (Graphpad Prism)			
mean	4.949		
sd	2.027		
n	137		
5% lognorm	1.61	5.03	3.0
5% students t distr.	1.59	4.91	
Non parametric "fit"			
5%	1.20	3.33	3.3

The values from the Excel log normal and students t-test distributions come close to the values mentioned in the original publication. The TTC value of 3.0 mg/kg bw/day for Cramer class I is slightly conservative when compared to the non-parametric derivation (3.3 mg/kg bw/day) and the lognormal and student t-distributions (3.29 and 3.21 resp.) However, using a log normal fit and deriving the 5th percentile from this fitted distribution leads to a significantly higher TTC value of 5 mg/kg bw/day. The value as used in the TTC opinions by EFSA (3.0 mg/kg bw/day) is conservative as all estimates are (slightly) above this value. A visual representation shows a sufficient fit of the data to the log normal distribution (from the Graphpad Prism analysis):

Cramer class II (moderately toxic)

Values reproduced from the Munro dataset for the subclass of Cramer class II substances (28 substances) gives the following values for the TTC:

	In transformed NOEL	NOEL TTC (mg/kg bw/day)	NOEL TTC Munro 1996 (mg/kg bw/day)
Cramer Class II			
mean	3.31	27.40	26
sd	2.03		
n	28		
5% lognorm	-0.03	0.97	0.91
5% students t distr.	-0.15	0.86	
log normal fit (Graphpad Prism)			
mean	3.204	24.63	
sd	2.062		
n	28		
5% lognorm	-0.19	0.83	0.9
5% students t distr.	-0.31	0.73	
Non parametric "fit"			
5%	0.47	1.60	1.6

Again the values derived from the excel distribution functions are very close to the original value reported by Munro and used in the EFSA opinions on TTC. The fitted distribution from Graphpad gives us slightly lower (more conservative) TTC values, which is due to small number of substances in this Cramer class, leading to a larger uncertainty in the log normal distribution fit. This is also visible in the graphic representation of the log normal distribution fit from Graphpad Prism:

Cramer class III (high toxicity)

Values reproduced from the Munro dataset for the subclass of Cramer class III substances (448 substances) gives the following values for the TTC:

	In transformed NOEL	NOEL TTC (mg/kg bw/day)	NOEL TTC Munro 1996 (mg/kg bw/day)
Cramer Class III			
mean	2.26	9.56	9
sd	2.50		
n	448		
5% lognorm	-1.86	0.16	0.15
5% students t distr.	-1.87	0.15	
log normal fit (Graphpad Prism)			
mean	2.318		
sd	2.462		
n	448		
5% lognorm	-1.73	0.18	0.15
5% students t distr.	-1.74	0.18	
Non parametric "fit"			
5%	-2.01	0.13	0.12

All different approaches lead to a very good reproduction of the values reported in the Cramer classification. The large number of substances also allows for a very good fit of the data, as visible in the graphic representation of the Class III data with the GraphPad Prism log normal distribution fit:

Calculation of TTC values for the Euromix Inventory

For all substances in the EuroMix Inventory the ToxTree software was applied to determine the Cramer class. The 5th percentiles from the Munro analysis (Munro, 1995) were assigned to the substances according to their Cramer Class. These assigned “TTC-based NOAEL substitutes” can directly be used in a deterministic approach to risk calculations in the EuroMix MCRA tool, by using these values to derive a Relative Potency Factor by dividing them with the NOAEL from the reference compound.

Sometimes different results in the assignment of the Cramer classes can occur depending on the software implementation used. It was noted that as much as ~10% of the substances is classified differently between ToxTree and (older versions) of the OECD QSAR Application Toolbox. Especially interpretation of aromaticity of hetero-atom containing ring systems, and the different versions of the “pick-lists” of naturally occurring substances can lead to different results. It is hard to say which software is “better” as this has to be evaluated for individual cases. For the EuroMix inventory only the ToxTree software (version 2.6.13) with Decision Tree “Cramer rules, with extensions” has been applied. The results are included in the EuroMix Inventory database with all other *in silico*, *in vitro* and *in vivo* test data.

The use of CAG specific TTC-like values to estimate relative potency factors

The TTC based estimate of the relative potency factor as described in the previous sections is based on the distribution of NOELs *for any effect* seen in repeated dose toxicity testing. However, the relative potency factor should actually be based on the No Effect level for the specific effect that belongs to the CAG. Using distributions of NOELs established for specific effects (organ level- CAG level 1, or phenotype of effect, CAG level 2) and deriving a 5th percentile from these effect specific NOEL distributions could be a first refinement of the general TTC-based estimation of the relative potency factor .

This requires deriving new TTC-like values from well evaluated datasets. The EFSA CAG-evaluations of the Plant Protection Products (PPPs) could serve this purpose, as these datasets have been well evaluated, a key study is selected and the occurrence of the CAG specific effects and the dose(s) at which these occur is described. As an example the NOAELs for the CAG hepatotoxicity, phenotype steatosis for the PPPs in the EFSA CAG evaluation have been used to derive a Steatosis specific TTC value.

NOAELs Steatosis

This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

For 98 substances that were actually showing Steatosis as an effect in the database of ~400 Pesticides the 5th percentile of the NOAELs for Steatosis is estimated to 0.5 mg/kg bw/day. Actually all of the evaluated pesticides are evaluated to fall in the Cramer class III (high toxicity), making it impossible to derive Steatosis specific values for anything else then Cramer Class III. The Steatosis Cramer Class III value should be compared to the 5th percentile of NOELs derived for Cramer III (high toxicity) class of compounds taking into account any effect seen in repeated dose toxicity testing. That value is 0.15 mg/kg bw/day.

This means that the relative potency factor derived from the generalized TTC approach is a factor of 3 ($0.5/0.15 = 3.33$) more conservative than a relative potency factor derived from the 5th percentile of NOAELs for the CAG level 2 specific effect of Steatosis. One could argue that this factor of 3 would also be applicable to the Cramer classes I and II, leading to Steatosis TTC based NOAEL values of 2.7 mg/kg bw/day for Cramer class II and a value of 9 mg/kg bw/day for the Cramer class I compounds.

It should be noted that this exercise was currently performed with a subset of the whole CAG evaluation dataset from EFSA, and only as an example of how the general TTC-based relative potency factor estimation can be refined to a more CAG specific relative potency factor estimate.

The use of Molecular Docking Binding Energies to estimate relative potency factors

The results from computer based molecular docking analysis is reported in a binding energy of the ligand (the substance we are interested in) to the receptor (e.g. a liver nuclear receptor involved in a hepatotoxicity pathway, or the estrogen receptor in endocrine disruption). This binding energy bears a direct relationship with the (expected) potency of a substance, as it is directly related to the receptor/ligand dissociation constant K_i , (see e.g. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Binding_constant) through

$$K_i = e^{-(dG/RT)}$$

with dG being the delta Gibbs free energy, i.e. the binding energy; R the universal molar gas constant and T the temperature in Kelvin. We cannot directly derive an absolute potency from these values of the dissociation constant, but we can use this relationship to establish *relative* potencies, as a substance that is binding 10 times better to the receptor (i.e. has a K_i ten times higher), is also expected to be 10 times more potent. We ignore in this assumption the (finite, and variable) concentration of receptors in different tissues, i.e. we assume low concentrations of the ligand with respect to the receptors.

If we now have two substances which exert their toxicological effect through the binding of the same (nuclear) receptor in the organism, one (reference) substance with a known potency (NOAEL) e.g. from in vivo experiments, we can calculate the relative potency of the second by comparing the binding energies from the molecular docking experiments as follows:

$$\text{NOAEL(unknown)} = \text{NOAEL(reference)} * e^{-(dG(\text{reference})/RT) - (dG(\text{unknown})/RT)}$$

With the NOAELs expressed in mmol/kg bw/day. Using a temperature of 293 Kelvin and the molar gas constant of 1.987 cal/Kmol the relative potency becomes 5.63 for each kcal/mol difference in binding energy.

To calculate the relative potency factor in terms of NOAELs one also has to correct for differences in molecular weight by multiplying with the ratio of the Molecular Weight of the two substances. This leads to:

$$\text{NOAEL(unknown)} = \text{NOAEL(reference)} * [\text{MW(unknown)/MW(reference)}] * e^{-(dG(\text{unknown})/RT) - (dG(\text{reference})/RT)}$$

Conclusions

The dataset from the original Munro publication (as attached to this deliverable in Annex I) allows reproduction of the original TTC values derived in the Munro publication and still used and recommended today in EFSA opinions. Either the lognormal distribution 5th percentile with its confidence intervals, or direct Monte Carlo simulation sampling from the dataset and its distribution over the three Cramer Classes should allow to reproduce sufficiently closely the EFSA recommended TTC values, and treat the TTC values probabilistically in the EuroMix risk assessment tool.

The 5th percentiles from the distributions are used directly as “substitute” NOAELs” instead of the derived TTC values, which also include an extra safety factor of 100. This reflects the direct use of NOAELs derived from animal studies for derivation of Relative Potency Factors, as no safety or assessment factors are applied to these NOAELs either.

The separate categories “Genotoxic carcinogens” and “Organo-phosphates and carbamates” with their own (lower) TTC values are not used in the EuroMix concept, as the effects on which the TTC values are based (genotoxicity and AcetylCholine Esterase inhibition) are not relevant for the Cumulative Assessment Groups used as case studies in EuroMix (Liver toxicity, Developmental Toxicity and Endocrine Disruption). For the CAG Neurotoxicity the AChE inhibition effect is very relevant, and the TTC approach for deriving first tier relative potency factors in Mixtures Risk Assessment should take into account this separate (lower) TTC value for organo-phosphates and –carbamates in this specific CAG.

CAG specific (level 1 and/or level 2) TTC like threshold values for the estimation of relative potency factors can be derived, in effect forming a next tier (slightly less conservative) by using the EFSA CAG evaluation datasets and deriving 5th percentiles of the distribution of NOAELs for specific effects. This has been shown for Steatosis to make the estimate of the relative potency factors a factor of 3.33 less conservative compared to Threshold values based on any effect (coming from the Munro analysis).

Calculations from the molecular docking experiments can – for substances that are assumed to exert their effect via binding to the same (nuclear) receptor – be used to establish more realistic relative potency factors. The use of docking models can be seen as a refinement of the use of TTC based relative potency factors.

References

- Cramer GM, Ford RA & Hall RL (1978). Estimation of Toxic Hazard - A Decision Tree Approach. Food and Cosmetics Toxicology 16, 255-276.
- Eberini et al. 2011. J Comput Aided Mol Des, 2011, 25(8):743-52.
- EuroMix 2016. EuroMix Deliverable 2.2 Report on the use of in-silico methods for the prioritisation of substances and mixtures thereof.
- EFSA 2012. Scientific Opinion on Exploring options for providing advice about possible human health risks based on the concept of Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC). EFSA Scientific Committee. European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Parma, Italy. EFSA Journal 2012;10(7):2750
- EFSA 2016a. EFSA (European Food Safety Authority) and WHO (World Health Organization), 2016. Review of the Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) approach and development of new TTC decision tree. EFSA supporting publication 2016: EN-1006. 50 pp.
- EFSA 2016b. EFSA (European Food Safety Authority) and WHO (World Health Organization), 2016. Outcome of a public consultation on the conclusions and recommendations of the EFSA–WHO workshop on the Threshold of Toxicological Concern approach. EFSA supporting publication 2016: EN-1000. 71 pp.
- Lapenna 2011. Lapenna S & Worth A (2011). Analysis of the Cramer classification scheme for oral systemic toxicity - implications for its implementation in Toxtree. EUR 24898 EN. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- Munro 1996. MUNRO IC, RA FORD, E KENNEPOHL and JG SPRENGER. Correlation of Structural Class with No-Observed-Effect Levels: A Proposal for Establishing a Threshold of Concern. Food and Chemical Toxicology 34 (1996) 829-867
- OECD 2017. OECD QSAR Application Toolbox version 4.1. Latest versions and background information available online from <https://www.qsartoolbox.org/>
- REACH 2012. Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment Chapter R.8: Characterisation of dose [concentration]-response for human health. Version data 24.11.2012. Available from https://echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/13632/information_requirements_r8_en.pdf/e153243a-03f0-44c5-8808-88af66223258
- ToxTree 2017. Toxic Hazard Estimation by decision tree approach, Version 2.16.3 dd. 23-03-2015, available from https://eurl-ecvam.jrc.ec.europa.eu/laboratories-research/predictive_toxicology/qsar_tools/toxtree

Annex 1. NOAEL Dataset used for determining TTC (Munro, 1996)

The first 2 of the total of 613 substances are given as an example. The whole dataset is attached as an excel worksheet.

Munro_dataset_original.xlsx

ID_Munro	NAME_Munro_1996	Structural Class (Cramer classification)	CAS_RN	Species tested	Exposure duration	Studytype	Exposure route - short	Exposure route - long	Endpoint type - short	Endpoint type - long
1	Acetic acid	1	64-19-7	rat	105.0	sub	orl	Oral - drinking water	nofx	no effects
2	Acetoin	1	513-86-0	rat	91.0	sub	orl	Oral - drinking water	mult	multiple effects
3	Acetone	1	67-64-1	rat	90.0	sub	gav	Oral - gavage	owt	organ weighth changes

Cont'd

Doses Given by Author	Dose Comments	LOEL Munro	NOEL Munro	NOEL_calculated_Munro_mg/kg/day	NOEL_calculated_chronic (factor 3 applied to sub) mg/kg/day	References	Smiles
0.01,0.1,0.25,0.5% [c]	Conversions were calculated using standard values.	none	none	726	242	Sollmann, 1921	O=C(C)O
0, 750, 3000, 12,000 ppm [a]	Conversions provided by author.	1286.0	330.0	330	110	Gaunt et al., 1972a	CC(=O)C(C)O
0, 100, 500, 2500 mg/kg/day		500.0	100.0	100	33.333333	US EPA, 1986a	CC(=O)C